

Internet Purchases in European Union Countries: Multiple Linear Regression Approach

Authors : Ksenija Dumičić, Anita Čeh Časni, Irena Palić

Abstract : This paper examines economic and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) development influence on recently increasing Internet purchases by individuals for European Union member states. After a growing trend for Internet purchases in EU27 was noticed, all possible regression analysis was applied using nine independent variables in 2011. Finally, two linear regression models were studied in detail. Conducted simple linear regression analysis confirmed the research hypothesis that the Internet purchases in analysed EU countries is positively correlated with statistically significant variable Gross Domestic Product per capita (GDPpc). Also, analysed multiple linear regression model with four regressors, showing ICT development level, indicates that ICT development is crucial for explaining the Internet purchases by individuals, confirming the research hypothesis.

Keywords : European union, Internet purchases, multiple linear regression model, outlier

Conference Title : ICBEMS 2014 : International Conference on Business, Economics and Management Sciences

Conference Location : Madrid, Spain

Conference Dates : March 27-28, 2014